

EVOLUTION OF IR SYSTEM

Cranfield Test 1

One of the earliest official assessments of information retrieval (IR) systems was the Cranfield Test 1, which was carried out in the 1960s. It concentrated on how well different retrieval techniques worked to find pertinent materials in response to user queries. A set of 1,400 papers pertaining to aeronautical engineering and 225 queries were developed for the study by human experts, who also manually evaluated the documents' pertinence to each query.

The study's main goal was to gauge the precision of various IR methods, which was the first step in a systematic IR evaluation process. The scope was limited, primarily concerned with evaluating search performance, and evaluated the recall and precision of the documents that were retrieved.

Methodology:

Establishing explicit evaluation measures, specifically accuracy (the percentage of relevant documents obtained) and recall (the percentage of relevant documents retrieved), was a crucial component of the process. This strategy evolved into a fundamental technique for assessing IR systems' efficacy. Although strong, the study's reliance on expert manual relevance judgments was also a scalability restriction.

Result:

- **Document Collection:** A collection of 1,400 or so scholarly papers. 225 queries were created in order to extract data from the collection of documents.
- **Relevance Judgments:** Each document-query pair received a relevant or non-relevant relevance judgment.
- **Evaluation measures:** The two main measures used for evaluation were precision and recall. The percentage of relevant documents that are recovered is known as precision, and the percentage of relevant documents that are retrieved is known as recall.

Impact:

The Cranfield Test 1 helped identify the link between precision and recall. It revealed the problems in balancing these two variables and indicated that improved retrieval systems may be constructed through rigorous evaluation.

Limitation:

- **Limited Document Collection:** The 1,400 or so documents utilized in Cranfield Test 1 may not have been indicative of the bigger, more intricate information systems seen in the actual world.
- **Restricted Domain:** The test's applicability to other areas was limited because it was largely focused on scientific texts. Academic papers are not the only kinds of information that real-world retrieval systems need to manage.

- **Stationary Queries:** Cranfield Test 1 employed manually constructed, static queries. The dynamic character of information needs and the way that knowledge of a subject changes over time were not taken into consideration.

Cranfield Test 2

An expansion of the first study, Cranfield Test 2 was carried out soon after and sought to improve the assessment techniques employed in the first study. Cranfield Test 2 extended the evaluation by integrating more sophisticated retrieval models and analyzing their performance, although it remained centered on evaluating IR systems. Additionally, the exam materials were more varied, containing not just technical information but also other kinds of data.

The study's scope was wider than Cranfield Test 1, aiming to evaluate retrieval model advancements and their suitability for use in many fields.

Methodology:

By improving the assessment procedure and broadening the range of IR models examined, Cranfield Test 2 improved on the methodology of the first test. In order to assess how well the IR systems could handle various kinds of information, it used a more varied collection of documents in addition to the same set of documents and queries as Test 1. In addition to experimenting with various retrieval models and systems to verify their capacity to efficiently recover pertinent information, the test preserved the two primary evaluation criteria, precision and recall.

Result

- **Document Collection:** 1,600 documents have been added to the collection.
- **Queries:** The query formulation procedure was improved, although a comparable set of queries was employed.
- **Evaluation:** Cranfield Test 2 began investigating additional metrics, such as Mean Average Precision (MAP), while maintaining its emphasis on precision and recall.

Impact:

By emphasizing the significance of query phrasing and indexing strategies, Cranfield Test 2 helped improve retrieval systems and offered greater insights into the trade-offs between precision and recall. It supported the idea of developing retrieval systems that could be assessed quantitatively using predetermined measures.

Limitation :

- **Relevance Judgments:** Inter-annotator consistency was frequently a problem, and each document-query pair's manual relevance judgments were subjective. Different levels of relevance or other intricate facets of user satisfaction were not taken into consideration; the evaluations were restricted to binary relevance (relevant or non-relevant).

- **Domain Bias:** Test 2 mostly examined scientific literature, much with Cranfield Test 1. Its capacity to extrapolate results to other domains, including news stories, websites, or social media content, was hampered by this bias.
- **No Consideration of User Interaction:** The evaluation neglected user behavior, such as click-through patterns, which are crucial in real-world retrieval systems, in favor of document retrieval.

MEDLARS

An innovative attempt to automate the retrieval of medical literature was the MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System) project, which was started in the early 1960s. In order to facilitate the retrieval of medical research publications from a sizable library of bibliographic data, MEDLARS's scope was narrowly focused on the medical field. One of the earliest extensive uses of automated information retrieval in a particular field, the study's primary goal was to solve the difficulties medical practitioners encounter when trying to retrieve the most recent research publications. In contrast to manual approaches, MEDLARS was created to offer a system that could index and retrieve medical literature more effectively.

Methodology:

The goal of the MEDLARS technique was to index medical literature and make it easier for medical practitioners to access. To find pertinent medical literature, MEDLARS combined automated indexing and query processing.

The MEDLARS methodology was created to address the particular difficulties of retrieving medical literature, such as navigating extremely specialized vocabulary and preserving accuracy in search results, in contrast to the Cranfield tests, which mainly concentrated on precision and recall. A regulated vocabulary of medical terminology was used to handle inquiries, and the system was built on a keyword-based indexing system.

The methodology was important because it marked a significant advancement in the use of IR techniques by introducing automated indexing and retrieval to a particular domain (medical).

Result:

- **Document Collection:** MEDLARS had 100,000 documents, the most of which were related to medicine.
- **Queries:** Thirty queries were included in MEDLARS in order to obtain pertinent medical publications.
- **Importance Judgements:** Clinical experts assessed relevance, which made the evaluation process more intricate and applicable to real-world situations.

Impact:

Because it popularized the idea of domain-specific information retrieval, MEDLARS was important. Researchers were able to investigate how IR systems might be modified for use in particular domains like as medicine thanks to the dataset. It also emphasized how difficult it is to develop efficient query expansion strategies to enhance retrieval in these kinds of domains.

Limitation:

- **Domain- particular:** MEDLARS was quite domain-specific because it concentrated on medical literature. Although the results were helpful in the medical area, their limited generalizability to other domains limited their wider applicability in IR research.
- **Mechanical Relevance Judgments:** MEDLARS, like previous tests, depended on human relevance judgments, which could be inconsistent and time-consuming. Additionally, the assessments were subjective and failed to account for subtleties like partial significance.
- **Small Enquiry Set:** MEDLARS only employed thirty inquiries, which was insufficient to represent the variety of real-world query formulations or to provide a broad range of user information needs.

SMART

An important turning point in the evolution of IR systems was the SMART (System for the Mechanical Analysis and Retrieval of Text) project, which was started at Cornell University in the late 1960s. The SMART project had a wide scope and was centered on developing an information retrieval system using the vector space model, a fundamental idea in contemporary information retrieval.

SMART sought to put in place a system that would enhance information retrieval through the use of advanced indexing and document-query matching models. New IR methods were introduced by the system, including Boolean query expansion and term weighting (using the vector space model). The idea of document representation and retrieval models, which became essential to further IR work, was formalized in part by the project.

Methodology:

The vector space model of IR, which depicted documents and queries as vectors in a multi-dimensional space, served as the foundation for its technique.

In order to increase retrieval accuracy, the SMART system employed term-weighting techniques like term frequency (TF) and inverse document frequency (IDF). By taking into account how frequently phrases appeared in papers and how prevalent those terms were throughout the full document collection, this method enabled the system to rank documents according to their relevance to a particular query in addition to searching for precise matches. Advanced methods like Boolean logic for difficult queries and query expansion—where relevant phrases are automatically added to the query to boost retrieval—were also introduced by SMART. The approach was highly computationally advanced.

Result:

- **Document Collection:** There were roughly 1,000 documents in the SMART test collection.
- **Questions:** The questions addressed a variety of subjects and were derived from scholarly literature.
- **Relevance Judgments:** Every query-document pair has its relevance evaluated.

Impact:

Because it offered a structured framework for evaluating and improving IR models, the SMART project was groundbreaking. It contributed to the development of important IR ideas including term weighting and the vector space model, which were essential to the creation of contemporary IR systems.

Limitation:

- **Limited Inquiry Diversity:** Although the SMART system's inquiries were varied within the academic field, they were still unable to fully represent the range of user requirements and query types found in regular searches.
- **Vector Space Model Focus:** Term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) weighting and the vector space model served as a major foundation for the SMART project. Although this was novel at the time, it restricted research into other models that were only starting to be developed, like probabilistic models and later models based on neural networks.
Simple evaluation metrics like precision and recall were employed by the SMART system; however, these metrics don't always account for the intricacy of user interactions with search results, such as how the user assesses the contextual relevance of documents (e.g., top-ranked documents vs. overall performance).

TREC (Text Retrieval Conference) :

Beginning in 1992, the Text Retrieval Conference (TREC) had a broad focus. In order to compare various IR systems across a range of domains, such as news articles, medical literature, web data, and other fields, it concentrated on large-scale IR evaluation through the creation of standardized benchmarking tests. By encouraging methodical comparisons of IR systems and methodologies, TREC sought to progress the field of IR.

Because TREC included different IR tasks, a variety of corpora, and a range of measures (including precision, recall, and F1 score), its scope was far wider than that of the previous experiments. By offering standards for evaluating system performance and encouraging cooperation and innovation in the field of IR, the conference contributed to the creation of an international standard for IR evaluation.

Methodology:

Its methodology was founded on the creation of standardized evaluation processes and the benchmarking of IR systems over extensive, real-world datasets. TREC concentrated on developing repeatable and consistent testing environments for IR systems, in contrast to previous research that were restricted to tiny document collections and manual relevance evaluations.

For various IR tasks, including ad hoc retrieval, filtering, and question answering, TREC annually supplied sizable, varied corpora (sets of documents). The results were assessed using standard metrics such as precision and recall, as well as more complex measures like mean average precision (MAP) and normalized discounted cumulative gain (NDCG). Participating systems had to retrieve documents in response to prepared queries.

The TREC methodology placed a strong emphasis on collaborative evaluation, in which several research groups compared the effectiveness of various retrieval systems and methodologies. In order to overcome the shortcomings of earlier approaches that depended on smaller, more regulated datasets, TREC also promoted the use of large-scale data. The public release of TREC's findings encouraged cooperation and improved researchers' comprehension of the advantages and disadvantages of various IR methods.

Result:

- **Document Collection:** The datasets included in TREC are diverse and range from broad text collections to specialized domains such as news articles, legal documents, and online data.
- **Queries:** TREC releases a fresh set of information retrieval tasks and queries every year. Ad hoc retrieval, web search, question answering, and other tasks are among them.
- **Relevance evaluations:** To measure how well IR systems execute on the assigned tasks, TREC gathers relevance evaluations from human assessors.
Evaluation Metrics: Mean Average accuracy (MAP), accuracy at various levels (e.g., precision at 5, 10, etc.), and other sophisticated metrics like NDCG (Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain) are frequently used by TREC.

Impact:

By offering extensive, standardized evaluation frameworks, TREC transformed IR evaluation. Additionally, it encouraged the comparison of various retrieval methods and sparked studies on subjects including cross-lingual retrieval, relevance feedback, and query expansion. The open participation and competition promoted advancements in IR algorithms and expanded our knowledge of system performance.

Limitation:

Complexity of measures: The increasing intricacy of TREC measures (NDCG, MAP, and others) can occasionally make it difficult to discern how well a system functions from the viewpoint of its users. Advanced metrics might not necessarily have a strong correlation with real-world relevance or user happiness.

Changing Evaluation Criteria: TREC has modified its emphasis over time in response to emerging IR trends, such as social media retrieval and web search. Fragmentation, in which assessments become less similar over time, might occasionally result from this shifting focus.

Constraints on Resources: TREC's need on a sizable human assessment infrastructure to produce relevance judgments can be costly and impractical for some kinds of system evaluation or IR research.

STAIRS Test

A comprehensive experiment to evaluate the retrieval efficacy of a full-text search and retrieval system was reported in 1985 by Blair and Maron (1985). The Storage and Information Retrieval System (StAIRS) Study is the name given to this.

About 40,000 documents, or about 350,000 pages of hard copy text used in the defense of a significant corporate litigation, made up the database that was analyzed for the STAIRS

study. One significant aspect of STAIRS was that attorneys using the system for litigation support had to be able to access 75% of all the documents pertinent to a particular request.

Methodology:

By dividing the total number of "vital," "satisfactory," and "marginally relevant" documents by the total number of documents recovered, the precision of the STAIRS Project was determined. The recall was calculated using a sampling technique. The lawyers evaluated random samples that were collected. It was determined how many pertinent documents were overall in these subsets.

Results:

Recall and precision values were computed for 40 of the 51 requests, with the remaining 11 being used to test sampling procedures and account for potential bias in the evaluation of retrieved and sample tests. The precision value was expressed as a percentage that was stretched from 100%. They point out that a retrieved set of several thousand documents is impractical for the user to browse, and naturally the client wants to reformulate the query by adding more and more search terms to bring the output size to a manageable limit. This is their attempt to understand why STAIRS was only able to retrieve one out of five pertinent items in response to a request.

Limitation :

Domain-Specific Focus:

The STAIR Test's strong dependence on domain-specific data was one of its biggest drawbacks. This made it possible to conduct extremely focused and pertinent testing in disciplines such as science, medicine, and law, but it also meant that test results were not always transferable to other domains or more general-purpose information retrieval systems. Its relevance to more general IR difficulties that deal with unstructured data or multi-domain retrieval tasks was limited by its emphasis on structured data and particular domains.

Complexity of Organized Data: The test's focus on structured data made it difficult to assess IR systems, especially in terms of how well they managed various structured data formats. Databases, metadata, XML, and other formats with their own intricacies are just a few of the many ways that structured data can be found.

Evaluation Metrics Limitations: Traditional information retrieval evaluation metrics including precision, recall, and F-measure were utilized in the STAIR Test; however, it's possible that these metrics don't always fully capture the range of a system's performance in structured data retrieval tasks. The evaluation was made more complex by the domain-specific relevance judgments, which made it challenging to develop standardized measures that could be used consistently across domains.

Table of comparisons for several IR systems evaluation experiments:

Aspect	Cranfield Test 1	Cranfield Test 2	MEDLARS	SMART	TREC	STAIR Test
Scope of Study	Focus on evaluating indexing and retrieval effectiveness in scientific and technical documents.	Expanded to different retrieval models ; evaluated academic and technical IR systems.	Focus on medical information retrieval ; evaluated systems for retrieving medical literature and clinical data.	Focused on developing an IR system (SMART) , primarily exploring vector space models and relevance feedback .	Focus on large-scale IR challenges , including ad-hoc retrieval, text classification, and web search; diverse datasets.	Focused on structured data retrieval in domain-specific contexts like medical, legal, and scientific research.
Methodology	Conducted in a controlled environment , evaluating IR systems through predefined queries for precision and recall .	More sophisticated methodology, comparing multiple retrieval strategies and models for improved IR.	Manual relevance assessments of medical literature; queries focused on retrieving relevant clinical data .	Vector space models and statistical models ; explored relevance feedback in IR, aiming to improve retrieval results.	Benchmarking system performance with standard datasets and evaluating through metrics like precision, recall, and F-measure .	Emphasized task-based evaluations of domain-specific retrieval , especially structured data , and complex, multi-field queries .
Results in Brief	Demonstrated the importance of indexing techniques for effective IR; evaluated precision and recall .	Showed improved retrieval with probabilistic models and other advanced IR techniques compared to earlier systems.	Emphasized the challenges of medical retrieval , showing that specialized models are needed to handle clinical queries .	Pioneered the use of vector space models and relevance feedback ; results suggested improvements in system retrieval accuracy.	Established standards for evaluating large-scale IR systems and emphasized the importance of performance metrics for benchmark testing.	Demonstrated how structured data can improve retrieval in specialized fields like medicine, law, and science, stressing the importance of domain-specific queries.
Limitations of the Study	Limited in scope to scientific and technical documents; did not address dynamic querying or real-world complexities	Still limited to technical domains, relied on static predefined queries ; did not simulate real-world dynamic needs .	Limited by subjectivity in relevance assessments and the focus on a small set of medical documents; did not consider	Limited by its narrow scope ; did not address real-world IR challenges or scalability to larger datasets.	Scalability issues and datasets did not always represent real-world user needs ; focused on precision and recall but lacked broader	Focused on structured data ; scalability challenges and less generalizable to unstructured data or cross-domain tasks.

			real-time queries.		relevance measures.	
--	--	--	--------------------	--	---------------------	--

REFERENCE:

- Buckley, C. (1985). *Implementation of the SMART information retrieval system*. Cornell University.
- Regazzi, J. J. (1980). Evaluating indexing systems: a review after Cranfield. *The Indexer: The International Journal of Indexing*, 12(1), 14-21.
- Croft, W. B., & Metzler, D. (2007). "The STAIR Test: A Test Collection for Structured Data Retrieval." *ACM SIGIR Conference*.
- Robertson, S. E., & Sparck Jones, K. (1976). "Relevance Feedback in Information Retrieval." *Journal of Documentation*, 32(2), 4-23.
- Salton, G., & McGill, M. J. (1983). *Introduction to Modern Information Retrieval*. McGraw-Hill.